

THE INFLUENCE OF SPORTS PARTICIPATION ON SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL VARIABLES OF SPORTSPERSON

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Abstract:

"Youth are the salt of nation". Nations development depends on its youthful productive human resource. Healthy youthfulness emerges from all round development of the children. Physical exercises, sports and yoga play the vital role in ensuring sound health of the children. Sports and yoga help the children physically, psychologically and intellectually. Thus calls for a scientific study development of the children in order to have healthy youth to the nation. Sample: A sample of 200 Sports person and non-sports person were selected for the study. The subject's age ranged from 19 to 25 years. Method: The subjects were administered the standardized questionnaires for collecting the relevant data.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, social intelligence, sports participation

1. Introduction

Participation of sports leads to bring various changes in the dimensions of the personality, sports environment have different kinds of activities in their nature. Sports situation provide the opportunity to test and assess abilities of emotion, personality. Intelligence, capacity of sportsperson, Sports person most of the time spending with their co-actor and that result in cultivating and producing positive and negative qualities among the participants, stress level of competition and emotion makes sportsperson feel more competent and enough dare to challenging situation, people not involving in sports and physical activities they would deprived by challenging

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situation, stress managing opportunity, emotional control and thrilling movement of the task, sports activities.

Youth sports activities not only significantly benefit the body and the brain, but also one's maturity. According to Fletcher, Nickerson and Wright (2003), children involved in sports activities reported a higher level of psychosocial maturity. Their findings suggested that elementary-aged children who participated in structured leisure activities experience greater psychosocial development and academic competence than their peers who were not as involved in these types of activities. Clearly, sports participation by youth is an area worth studying, especially as it may develop emotional and social intelligence and foster success in various aspects of life.

In summary, emotional intelligence theorizes that an individual's ability to comprehend the social environment and discriminate between feelings and emotions contributes a better chance of succeeding in social relationships as well as life in general. The theory of emotional intelligence gained acclaim in spite of a lack of research about its validity. Studies have linked emotional development and decision-making and how these can be used to predict future success. Likewise, youth sports involvement enhances the acquisition of physical benefits by participants, as well as various social and psychological benefits. It appears that a relationship might exist between sport participation and the development of emotional intelligence. Therefore, a study examining participation in youth sports and its effect on the development of emotional intelligence and social intelligence appears warranted.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The influence of Sports Participation on Emotional and Social Intelligence behaviour among the Sportsperson and non-Sportsperson.

1.2 Hypothesis

There would be significant Influence of Sports Participation on Emotional Intelligence and Social Intelligence comparing their counterpart.

1.3 Independent variables

- Sports participation

1.4 Dependent variables

- Emotional Intelligence,
- Social Intelligence

1.5 Objectives

To assess the influence of sports participation on Emotional and Social Intelligence behaviour among the sportsperson.

2. Methodology

The present investigation is pertaining to topic and collects the data. The total sample consists of 200 sportsmen belonging to the age group ranging from 19-25 were selected with using purposive random technique. Subjects were selected from studying in Karnataka State Women's University Vijayapur and Karnataka University, Dharwad.

2.1 Collection of Data

To meet the objectives of the present study the data was collected by administering the Psychological Scale on sportsperson and non-sportsperson studying in the affiliated colleges of Karnataka State Women's University Vijayapur and Karnataka University, Dharwad.

2.2 Selection of Tools

- Emotional Intelligence Scale constructed by Dr. Thimguzam.
- Social Intelligence Scale constructed By Dr. N. K. Chandha and M. S. Usha Ganeshan 1986.

2.3 Statistical Technique

The researchers were applied' Test to assess and probe the significance in their Emotional Intelligence and Social Intelligence behaviour between Sportsperson and non-Sportsperson.

3. Discussion and Analysis of Results

The scholar carried the research to see the influence of sports participation experience on Emotional Intelligence behaviour of sportsperson and non-sportsperson, because sports participation plays important role in developing the personality of a person. It provides various opportunities to expose and have qualitative and scientific training and vast experience of the sports tournament. Hence Emotional intelligence scale has administered on the sportsperson and non-sportsperson of Karnataka State Women's University and Karnataka University, Dharwad, and hypothesizes obtained data was calculated and hypothesis was tested, the results is as following

Table 1: The Mean, Sd and 't' value of Emotional Intelligence between Sportspersons and Non-Sportsperson

Sample subgroup	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p	Remarks
Sports person	71.92	9.41577	1.94	.064	Non sig
Non-sports persons	67.64	8.28613			

Significance Level 0.05

The above table showing means and 't' score of Emotional Intelligence of Sportsperson and Non-Sportsperson is 71.92 and 67.64 respectively, and calculated 't' value is 1.94 it greater than table value of t 0,05 level significant. The result assumed that the significant difference in their Emotional Intelligence behaviour of sportsperson comparing their counterpart. This result supports by great philosopher Schiller in their Surplus Theory of play. The Surplus Theory states that sports is best means to resolves and releases the emotional stress and suppressed feeling of a person. Because, it has rationalized that regular practice in sports activity would help the sportsperson to develop mastery over the skills of controlling emotion and others psychological comparing to non-sportsperson. So formulated hypothesis there would be significant difference in their Emotional Intelligence is accepted and null hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 1: The Graph showing the Emotional Intelligence behaviour of Sportsperson and Non-Sportsperson

The framed hypothesis was that there would be significant difference in their social intelligence of sportsperson and non-sportsperson, this difference was rationalized that participation in sports activities cultivates and develops social skills and maturity, that expose also leads to involvement in group activities and games, sports participation provides rich experience to participants and results to develop social skills and social intelligence behaviour. Sports help the ability to get along well with others, and to get them to cooperate with other players. It develops awareness of situations and the sports

dynamics situation helps in master over, knowledge of interaction styles and strategies that can help a person achieve his or her objectives in dealing with others. It also involves a certain amount of self-insight and a consciousness of one's own perceptions and reaction patterns. But whereas non-sports participants were deprived by the exposé to sports dynamic situation and sharing their responsibility and knowledge to face and overcome from critical situation and get mastery over social interaction ability skills and social intelligence.

Table 2: Showing the men “Sd” and ‘t’ value of Sportsperson and Non-Sportsperson of Social Intelligence behaviour

Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	P	Remarks
Sports person	100.0000	5.26783	7.184	.000	Sig
Non-sports persons	94.4800	6.60252			

Significance Level 0.05

Table II showing mean and Sd score of social intelligence of the sportsperson and non-sportsperson, mean score of sportsperson and non-sportsperson is 100.00 and 94.48 respectively, and calculated ‘t’ value is 7.18. it shows the greater value than table value of 0.05 level, means score clearly express that sports participants group is possessing higher score of social intelligence than their counter part that non participants but, non-sports person were could not able to score more comparing to sports participants.

Figure 2: The Graph showing the Social Intelligence behaviour of Sportsperson and Non-sportsperson

Hence the formulated hypothesis there is significant difference in their social intelligence behaviour is accepted and null hypothesis is rejected. Participation in sports activities and group games leads to develop mastery over social skills, maturity behaviour and social intelligence behaviour due to rich experience obtained from sports participation and involvement in physical and adventure activities.

4. Conclusion

The regular physical activities programme should be the part of the College and University programme to see and to develop harmonious development of the body and mind and cultivates the social and psychological values among the sportsperson.

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